

On a note of the Smarandache power function ¹

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the Smarandache power function $SP(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n|m^m$, where m and n have the same prime divisors. The main purpose of this paper is to study the distribution properties of the k -th power of $SP(n)$ by analytic methods, obtain three asymptotic formulas of $\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^k$, $\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi((SP(n))^k)$ and $\sum_{n \leq x} d(SP(n))^k$ ($k > 1$), and supplement the relate conclusions in some references.

Keywords Smarandache power function, the k -th power, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and results

For any positive integer n , we define the Smarandache power function $SP(n)$ as the smallest positive integer m such that $n|m^m$, where n and m have the same prime divisors. That is,

$$SP(n) = \min \left\{ m : n|m^m, m \in \mathbb{N}^+, \prod_{p|m} p = \prod_{p|n} p \right\}.$$

If n runs through all natural numbers, then we can get the Smarandache power function sequence $SP(n)$: 1, 2, 3, 2, 5, 6, 7, 4, 3, 10, 11, 6, 13, 14, 15, 4, 17, 6, 19, 10, \dots . Let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_k^{\alpha_k}$, denotes the factorization of n into prime powers. If $\alpha_i < p_i$, for all α_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, r$), then we have $SP(n) = U(n)$, where $U(n) = \prod_{p|n} p$, \prod denotes the product over all different prime divisors of n . It is clear that $SP(n)$ is not a multiplicative function.

In reference [1], Professor F. Smarandache asked us to study the properties of the sequence $SP(n)$. He has done the preliminary research about this question literature [2] – [4], has obtained some important conclusions. And literature [2] has studied an average value, obtained the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} SP(n) = \frac{1}{2} x^2 \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(1+p)} \right) + O\left(x^{\frac{3}{2}+\varepsilon}\right).$$

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Literature [3] has studied the infinite sequence astringency, has given the identical equation:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{\mu(n)}}{(SP(n^k))^s} = \begin{cases} \frac{2^s + 1}{(2^s - 1)\zeta(s)}, & k = 1, 2; \\ \frac{2^s + 1}{(2^s - 1)\zeta(s)} - \frac{2^s - 1}{4^s}, & k = 3; \\ \frac{2^s + 1}{(2^s - 1)\zeta(s)} - \frac{2^s - 1}{4^s} + \frac{3^s - 1}{9^s}, & k = 4, 5. \end{cases}$$

And literature [4] has studied the equation $SP(n^k) = \phi(n), k = 1, 2, 3$ solubility ($\phi(n)$ is the Euler function), and has given all positive integer solution. Namely the equation $SP(n) = \phi(n)$ only has 4 positive integer solutions $n = 1, 4, 8, 18$; Equation $SP(n^3) = \phi(n)$ to have and only has 3 positive integer solutions $n = 1, 16, 18$. In this paper, we shall use the analysis method to study the distribution properties of the $k - th$ power of $SP(n)$, gave $\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^k, \sum_{n \leq x} \varphi((SP(n))^k)$ and $\sum_{n \leq x} d(SP(n))^k$ ($k > 1$), some interesting asymptotic formula, has promoted the literature [2] conclusion.

Specifically as follows:

Theorem 1.1. For any random real number $x \geq 3$ and given real number k ($k > 0$), we have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^k = \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{(k+1)\zeta(2)} x^{k+1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k(p+1)}\right) + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon});$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \frac{(SP(n))^k}{n} = \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{k\zeta(2)} x^k \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k(p+1)}\right) + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}),$$

where $\zeta(k)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, ε denotes any fixed positive number, and \prod_p denotes the product over all primes.

Corollary 1.1. For any random real number $x \geq 3$ and given real number $k' > 0$ we have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^{\frac{1}{k'}} = \frac{6k'\zeta(\frac{1+k'}{k'})}{(k'+1)\pi^2} x^{\frac{1+k'}{k'}} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+p)p^{\frac{1}{k'}}}\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{k'+2}{2k'}+\varepsilon}\right).$$

Specifically, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{4\zeta(\frac{3}{2})}{\pi^2} x^{\frac{3}{2}} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+p)p^{\frac{1}{2}}}\right) + O(x^{1+\varepsilon});$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^{\frac{1}{3}} = \frac{9\zeta(\frac{4}{3})}{2\pi^2} x^{\frac{4}{3}} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+p)p^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) + O(x^{\frac{5}{6}+\varepsilon}).$$

Corollary 1.2. For any random real number $x \geq 3$, and $k = 1, 2, 3$. We have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n)) = \frac{1}{2} x^2 \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(1+p)}\right) + O(x^{\frac{3}{2}+\varepsilon});$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^2 = \frac{6\zeta(3)}{3\pi^2} x^3 \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^2(1+p)}\right) + O(x^{\frac{5}{2}+\varepsilon});$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^3 = \frac{\pi^2}{60} x^4 \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^3(1+p)}\right) + O(x^{\frac{7}{2}+\varepsilon}).$$

Theorem 1.2. For any random real number $x \geq 3$, we have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \varphi((SP(n))^k) = \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{(k+1)\zeta(2)} x^{k+1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+p)p^k}\right) + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}),$$

where $\varphi(n)$ is the Euler function

Theorem 1.3. For any random real number $x \geq 3$, we have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} d((SP(n))^k) = B_0 x \ln^k x + B_1 x \ln^{k-1} x + B_2 x \ln^{k-2} x + \dots + B_{k-1} x \ln x + B_k x + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}).$$

where $d(n)$ is the Dirichlet divisor function and $B_0, B_1, B_2, \dots, B_{k-1}, B_k$ is computable constant.

§2. Lemmas and proofs

Suppose $s = \sigma + it$ and let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_k^{\alpha_k}, U(n) = \prod_{p|n} p$. Before the proofs of the theorem, the following Lemmas will be useful.

Lemma 2.1. For any random real number $x \geq 3$ and given real number $k \geq 1$, we have the asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (U(n))^k = \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{(k+1)\zeta(2)} x^{k+1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+p)p^k}\right) + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}).$$

Proof. Let Dirichlet's series

$$A(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(U(n))^k}{n^s},$$

for any real number $s > 1$, it is clear that $A(s)$ is absolutely convergent. Because $U(n)$ is the multiplicative function, if $\sigma > k + 1$, so from the Euler's product formula [5] we have

$$\begin{aligned} A(s) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(U(n))^k}{n^s} \\ &= \prod_p \left(\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(U(p^m))^k}{p^{ms}} \right) \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{p^k}{p^s} + \frac{p^k}{p^{2s}} + \dots \right) \\ &= \frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k(1+p^{s-k})} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function. Letting $R(k) = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k(1+p^{s-k})} \right)$. If $\sigma > k +$

$$1, |U(n)| \leq n, \left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(U(n))^k}{n^\sigma} \right| < \zeta(\sigma - k).$$

Therefore by Perron’s formula [5] with $a(n) = (U(n))^k$, $s_0 = 0$, $b = k + \frac{3}{2}$, $T = x^{k+\frac{1}{2}}$, $H(x) = x$, $B(\sigma) = \zeta(\sigma - k)$, then we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (U(n))^k = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{k+\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{k+\frac{3}{2}+iT} \frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} h(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}),$$

where $h(k) = \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^{k(1+p)}}\right)$.

To estimate the main term

$$\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{k+\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{k+\frac{3}{2}+iT} \frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} h(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds,$$

we move the integral line from $s = k + \frac{3}{2} \pm iT$ to $k + \frac{1}{2} \pm iT$, then the function

$$\frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} h(s) \frac{x^s}{s}$$

have a first-order pole point at $s = k + 1$ with residue

$$\begin{aligned} L(x) &= \operatorname{Res}_{s=k+1} \left(\frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} h(s) \right) \\ &= \lim_{s \rightarrow k+1} \left((s-k-1) \frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} h(s) \frac{x^s}{s} \right) \\ &= \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{(k+1)\zeta(s)} x^{k+1} h(k). \end{aligned}$$

Taking $T = x^{k+\frac{1}{2}}$, we can easily get the estimate

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left(\int_{k+\frac{1}{2}+iT}^{k+\frac{3}{2}+iT} + \int_{k+\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{k+\frac{3}{2}+iT} \right) \frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} h(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| &\ll \frac{x^{2k+1}}{T} = x^{k+\frac{1}{2}}, \\ \left| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{k+\frac{1}{2}-iT}^{k+\frac{1}{2}+iT} \frac{\zeta(s)\zeta(s-k)}{\zeta(2s-2k)} h(s) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \right| &\ll x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}. \end{aligned}$$

We may immediately obtain the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (U(n))^k = \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{(k+1)\zeta(2)} x^{k+1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+p)p^k}\right) + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}),$$

this completes the proof of the Lemma 2.1.

Lemma 2.2. For any random real number $x \geq 3$ and given real number $k \geq 1$, and positive integer α , then we have

$$\sum_{\substack{p^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha > p}} (\alpha p)^k \ll \ln^{2k+2} x.$$

Proof. Because $\alpha > p$, so $p^p < p^\alpha \leq x$, then

$$p < \frac{\ln x}{\ln p} < \ln x, \quad \alpha \leq \frac{\ln x}{\ln p},$$

also, $\sum_{n \leq x} n^k = \frac{x^{k+1}}{k+1} + O(x^k)$. Thus,

$$\sum_{\substack{p^{\alpha} \leq x \\ \alpha > p}} (\alpha p)^k = \sum_{p \leq \ln x} p^k \sum_{\alpha \leq \frac{\ln x}{p}} \alpha^k \ll \ln^{k+1} x \sum_{p \leq \ln x} \frac{p^k}{\ln^{k+1} p} \ll \ln^{k+1} x \sum_{p \leq \ln x} p^k.$$

Considering $\pi(x) = \sum_{p \leq x} 1$, by virtue of [5], $\pi(x) = \frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right)$. we can get from the Able

$$\sum_{p \leq x} p^k = \pi(x)x^k - k \int_2^x \pi(t)t^{k-1} dt.$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{p \leq \ln x} p^k = \frac{\ln^k x}{(k+1)} + O(\ln^{k-1} x) - k \int_2^{\ln x} \frac{t^k}{\ln t} dt + O\left(\int_2^{\ln x} \frac{t^k}{\ln^2 t} dt\right) = \frac{\ln^k x}{k+1} + O(\ln^{k-1} x).$$

Thus

$$\sum_{\substack{p^{\alpha} \leq x \\ \alpha > p}} (\alpha p)^k = \sum_{p \leq \ln x} p^k \sum_{\alpha \leq \frac{\ln x}{p}} \alpha^k \ll \ln^{k+1} x \sum_{p \leq \ln x} \frac{p^k}{\ln^{k+1} p} \ll \ln^{k+1} x \sum_{p \leq \ln x} p^k \ll \ln^{2k+2} x.$$

This completes the proof of the Lemma 2.2.

§3. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem.

Proof of Theorem 1.1. Let $A = \{n | n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_k^{\alpha_k}, \alpha_i \leq p_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, r\}$. When $n \in A : SP(n) = U(n)$; When $n \in \mathbb{N}^+ : SP(n) \geq U(n)$, thus

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^k - \sum_{n \leq x} (U(n))^k = \sum_{n \leq x} [(SP(n))^k - (U(n))^k] \ll \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ SP(n) > U(n)}} (SP(n))^k.$$

By the [2] known, there is integer α and prime numbers p , so $SP(n) < \alpha p$, then we can get according to Lemma 2.2

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ SP(n) > U(n)}} (SP(n))^k < \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ SP(n) > U(n)}} (\alpha p)^k \ll \sum_{n \leq x} \sum_{\substack{p^{\alpha} < x \\ \alpha > p}} \ll x \ln^{2k+2} x.$$

Therefore

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^k - \sum_{n \leq x} (U(n))^k \ll x \ln^{2k+2} x.$$

From the Lemma 2.1 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} (SP(n))^k &= \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{(k+1)\zeta(2)} x^{k+1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k(1+p)}\right) + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}) + O(x \ln^{2k+1} x) \\ &= \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{(k+1)\zeta(2)} x^{k+1} \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{1}{p^k(1+p)}\right) + O(x^{k+\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}). \end{aligned}$$

This proves Theorem 1.1.

Proof of Corollary. According to Theorem 1.1, taking $k = \frac{1}{k'}$ the Corollary 1.1 can be obtained. Take $k = 1, 2, 3$, and $\zeta(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{6}, \zeta(4) = \frac{\pi^4}{90}$, we can achieve Corollary 1.2. Obviously so is theorem [2].

Using the similar method to complete the proofs of Theorem 1.2 and Theorem 1.3.

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